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Towed open water testing of tethered coaxial turbine for hydrokinetic energy harvesting

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Abstract

With a growing need for energy sustainability, the interest in harnessing marine hydrokinetic (MHK) energy from ocean currents has grown significantly. One potential source is the Gulf Stream off the Cape Hatteras coastline which offers a great location for MHK energy converters. This study aims to assess the performance of a tethered dual rotor coaxial turbine and demonstrate the feasibility of the system in open water conditions simulating application in the Gulf Stream. The turbine used features two counter-rotating rotors that are mechanically coupled to a generator at the body and rotary shaft respectively to allow for passive torque cancellation. Testing saw the turbine being towed underwater in the Croatan Sound with three resistive loads of 5000 ohms, 1000 ohms, and 500 ohms with each load being towed at three speeds of 1 m/s, 1.25 m/s, and 1.5 m/s. The speeds selected for the tow test simulated the currents seen in the Gulf Stream. In these tests, the performance of the turbine was evaluated based on the flow speed, angular rotation, and power generation. The initial results demonstrate the ability of the turbine to perform successfully in the open water environment showcasing its capacity to reliably extract power from flowing water and withstand the challenges of operating in such an environment.

Keywords: Marine Hydrokinetic Energy; Coaxial Turbine; Renewable Energy; Gulf Stream; Ocean Currents

1. Introduction

In recent years, with rising awareness of the importance of clean and sustainable energy sources, the appeal of renewable energy has grown significantly. This surge had led to an increased interest in developing new ways for marine current energy conversion [1]. Efforts are intensifying to find economical ways to harness the abundant energy resources offered by the world's oceans. Researchers are exploring various types of marine energy as promising candidates for generating sustainable power. One notable form of this energy is marine hydrokinetic (MHK) energy, which is extracted from the movement of ocean currents. This method involves utilizing the continuous flow of these currents to rotate turbines, thereby producing electricity, a process that mirrors how wind energy is captured and converted by wind turbines [2]. Around the world, amongst the many locations where steady, potent ocean currents are present, the Gulf Stream stands out as an exceptionally accessible, persistent, and strong ocean current. North of the Florida Straits, Cape Hatteras is the closest location to the Gulf Stream along the east coast and has a maximum

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surface-current speed of more than 2 m/s with an offshore MHK power density found to average 798 W/m^2 , positioning it as a prime candidate for substantial and reliable energy source [3].

A solution presented here as a viable MHK energy converter is the tethered coaxial turbine. Composed of a pair of counter-rotating rotors with a central axis of rotation the turbine converts fluid kinetic energy into rotational energy and by extension generates electricity. Due to the nature of the operation of the turbine, the counter-rotating rotors allows the system to self-align with the direction of flow and produces zero net torque and angular momentum [4]. The coaxial turbine also has an added ability to operate in skew in the flow which was found to generate more net power compared to axial operation [4-6]. This increased power generation in skew flow is attributed to the fact that part of the downstream rotor moves out of the wake created by the upstream rotor, allowing it to interact with undisturbed, higher-energy flow. The goal of this work was to assess the tethered dual-rotor coaxial turbine design for practical, open-water conditions closely simulating operation in the Gulf Stream. A systematic experimental study was carried out to monitor how the system behaves under these conditions and to measure its performance and electricity generation potential during submerged operation.

2. Open water experiment

This section goes over the system design and experimental setup used for the first demonstration of a towed tethered coaxial turbine in a saline water environment. Previous tests conducted using the coaxial turbine prototype were in freshwater lakes [7] where operational feasibility and the ability to generate power were validated. With the goal to evaluate the power harvested by the turbine through mechanical rotation in the open water environment, changes were made to the prototype to facilitate field trial conditions. The dual rotor coaxial hydrokinetic turbine used for the open water test featured two identically sized rotors, each with three blades that rotate in opposite directions. The upstream blades positioned at the front of the turbine are coupled with the onboard generator body, while the downstream rotor at the rear of the turbine is linked to the generator's rotor shaft. To counter the torque created due to the differing fluid dynamics and blade rotational velocities between the upstream and downstream rotors, a coaxial design was adopted which had a common rotational axis, facilitating passive torque neutralization through the generator.

2.1 System Design

The prototype tethered turbine used for the saline water hydrokinetic energy harvesting demonstration was a dual rotor coaxial design with an onboard generator and electronic measurement suite. The turbine used was similar to the coaxial turbine design used for earlier freshwater testing [7], however, modifications were made to the electronic sensor suite, rotor blades, type of tether used, and the hub couplers in order to test in the harsher saline water environment. As seen in Fig. 1, the turbine is comprised of two primary modules, the electronic module which lies towards the front of the turbine, and the generator module which is towards the rear. The two modules are flanked by two aluminum rotor hubs that are used to mount and secure the three rotor blades upstream and downstream of the turbine. The rotor hubs were designed to allow for easy interchangeability of the blades. For the purpose of the saline water test, the hubs were further machined down to minimize their weight. On the ends of the rotor hubs, two hydrodynamic cones are mounted that act as the ballast used for controlling the buoyancy of the turbine system.

The electronic module, designed to be a dry section, houses the onboard data acquisition and energy management system. To make the module watertight, O-ring seals were used at the connecting components that seal off the two open ends of the cylinder. As a precaution to protect the electronics a secondary waterproof compartment to house the electronic suites was also used and placed inside the electronic module. The electrical components of note are the

Fig. 1. Detailed view of the coaxial dual-rotor turbine design [7].

rectification power board, a 1-axis analog gyro, and a Lord™ 3DM-CX5 IMU. The rectification power board is designed so that the resistive load or capacitor can be changed during the experiment. The 3DM-CX5 is used to provide global reference measurement along with attitude and orientation, while the analog gyro is used to measure angular rotation about the turbine axis of rotation.

The generator module, as the name suggests, houses the generator and magnetic disk with a hall effect sensor. Here the magnet disc and hall effect sensor are used to measure the relative angular rotation between the upstream and downstream rotors. This module is designed as a wet section, allowing water to fill the chamber. This was done to reduce the complexities and risks associated with waterproofing. To enable even flooding and to deter air pocket formation when the turbine is submerged and spinning, the chamber is equipped with two water entry ports. Both the electronic and generator modules are made using a hollow aluminum cylinder with a diameter of 10.8cm and a length of 24.8cm and 21.6cm, respectively. A module coupler is used to connect the ends of the two modules seen in the assembly in Fig. 1. The generator module electronics are connected to the electronic module sensor suite via a waterproof sub-con connector as seen in Fig. 2(a).

Fig. 2. (a) Elecectrical component assembly of the generator to the sensor suite; (b) Assembled turbine prior to open water deployment.

To ensure the system is strong and durable enough to withstand the increased forces and stresses encountered during testing in a saltwater environment, the various turbine body components, including the front and rear rotor mount hubs the casing or hull for the electronic and generator module, and the module coupler, were machined out of 6061 aluminum alloy. This material offered higher corrosion resistance and reduced weight compared to steel providing the desired mechanical properties. Further details about the system design can be found in [7].

As mentioned above, a key attribute of the turbine design is the ability to have passive torque cancellation. This is achieved in two parts. The first is by having the upstream and downstream rotor blades spin in opposing directions about the same central axis of rotation. The second is by attaching the rear rotor hub, downstream rotor blades, and the tail cone to the generator rotating shaft, and fixing the rest of the turbine body, including the two modules, upstream rotor blades, and nose cone, to the generator body. Due to this design characteristic the upstream rotor and entire turbine body before the rear rotor hub spins clockwise with the downstream rotor and rear rotor hub assembly spins counterclockwise.

Due to the nature of the testing environment, the focus on the blade design was towards structural strength and durability while providing performance at low Reynolds number flow. For this reason, an airfoil SG6040 was selected [8] with a constant chord of 3.8 cm and a blade span of 26 cm. To enhance the blade's robustness and improve its rigidity, a half-inch hollow aluminum rod was used as a spar and was inserted into the blade at the quarter chord and epoxied. The blade's base was further reinforced by increasing its thickness to provide additional structural stability. Since the blades were 3D printed using ABS material, the large chord helped to maximize the material used and add additional strength to the blade. The blades used can be seen in Fig. 2(b).

2.2 Experimental Setup

Open water tow testing of the tethered coaxial turbine was conducted in the Croatan sound near the North Carolina Coastal Studies Institute (CSI) seen in Fig. 3(b). This test location was chosen due to its ease of accessibility from the CSI docks as well as for the current flow rate and stable waters. As part of the test setup, the coaxial turbine was connected to a downrigger weight via a neutrally buoyant Blue Robotics cable, with the downrigger in turn being tied off at the boat via a Dyneema rope as can be seen in Fig. 3(a). High load bearing swivels were used at the connection points between the turbine and the downrigger. These swivels were used to prevent the twisting of the cable, isolating it from the rotating turbine. The length of the cable and the Dyneema rope were 9.15 m (30 ft) and 2.43 m (8 ft)

respectively. For the test, to mimic the flow of water currents, the turbine was towed behind a boat using predetermined lengths of cable at assigned speeds. To aid in testing, the turbine was set up to be positively buoyant. This added two benefits, the first being that in the event that the turbine becomes detached from the boat, it can be retrieved, and the second is, by having the center of gravity and center buoyancy located at different locations on the axis of rotation, skewed operation could be achieved which can result in better turbine performance [9]. Thus, in order to submerge the buoyant turbine during towed operation a downrigger weighing 13.6 kg (30lbs) was used.

Fig. 3. (a) Open water towed turbine test setup; (b) Testing location: Croatan sound.

3. Results and discussion

The tow test in the Croatan Sound was a big milestone for the device as it was the first demonstration of the operational feasibility of a coaxial turbine in an open water setting. Testing was conducted in two testing locations as seen in Fig. 3(b). These sites were chosen based on water depth and the water conditions for the test day. Testing started with the turbine first being assembled at the docks at CSI. The assembly process included measuring the salinity of the water and determining the density of water to adjust the buoyancy of the turbine so that it just floats on the surface. For the test day, the Specific gravity was recorded at 1.017 and the Salinity was measured at approximately 24 parts per thousand as seen in Fig. 4(a). Once assembly was completed, a mock run was conducted, where the turbine was deployed in the water to verify turbine operation, buoyancy, and test deployment strategies shown in Fig. 4(b).

Testing was conducted at a location with a maximum water depth of 5.48 m (18 ft). The turbine was operated at a depth of between 1.52 m (5 ft) and 1.82 m (6 ft) below the surface of the water. This depth was chosen to be sufficiently far from the sea floor to avoid debris, while being far enough below the surface of the water to reduce interaction of the turbine with the wake of the boat. For the test, three resistive loads of 5000 ohms, 1000 ohms, and 500 ohms were selected, with the lowest resistive load providing the highest generated power. Tow testing runs were conducted in sets of three speeds of 1 m/s, 1.25 m/s, and 1.5 m/s, for up to 10 minutes each of steady operation, similar to previous tow tests [7]. The relative tow speeds through water were measured using the onboard instrumentation aboard the CSI research vessel seen in Fig 3(a). These speeds were selected based on the average current speeds seen in the Gulf Stream off the North Carolina coast which average 1.09 m/s and can go up to 2 m/s [10]. After each set was completed, the turbine was retrieved, and the resistive load was changed.

Fig. 4. (a) Water salinity check using a refractometer; (b) Turbine assembly and deployment during testing.

Fig. 5(a)(b) shows the relative angular velocity measured between the upstream and downstream rotors and the corresponding voltage generated by the generator for a resistive load of 500 which provided the maximum efficiency. From both figures in Fig. 5, a relationship between the relative rotation rate of the rotor blades, the voltage generated, and the measured boat tow speeds can be seen.

Fig. 5. (a) Relative angular rotation at 500 ohms resistive load for varying boat tow speeds; (b) Voltage measured at 500 ohms resistive load for varying boat tow speeds.

For a constant tow speed, the rotation rate remains consistent. Furthermore, the data in the figure highlights that when the flow is stable, the voltage measurement remains stable as well. The trends shown clearly illustrated in the figures help in visualizing the direct proportionality between the flow speed, angular rotation, and voltage generation. With a max voltage measured at 16V, the prototype turbine generates 0.5W of power. This suggests that consistent and steady flows can lead to reliable and constant power generation.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, this work presents the first deployment of a prototype tethered coaxial turbine being towed in a saline open water environment. Testing in this environment included making updates to the turbine design by structurally strengthening and redesigning the rotor blades to sustain higher loads, employing a new underwater cable, and updating the sensor suite to measure higher rotational rates. During the tow tests conducted on the experimental unit, initial findings were gathered that showcased the capacity of a prototype hydrokinetic energy harvesting turbine to effectively extract power from flowing water currents. In addition to its ability to harness energy, the system exhibited strong resilience and effective waterproofing features, proving the feasibility of the design for use in a harsher open water environment. This test lays the groundwork for the final stage of the coaxial turbine operation with deployment in the Gulf Stream with power take-off, to demonstrate the ability of the system to actively send power via a cable during underwater operation.

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